

THE IMPACT OF CYBER THREATS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

Rustamov Alisher Bahadirovich

Associate Professor of TATU Karshi branch named after

Muhammad al-Khorazmi

arustamov_88@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10940216>

Abstract: As the economy shifts to digital and online models, threats are rapidly outstripping traditional approaches to data security. More than ever, governments and organizations are being asked to be proactive in building and adapting systems against these threats. This article examines the impact of cyber threats on the rapidly developing digital economy.

Keywords: Digital economy, threats, risk, privacy, information security, information, vulnerabilities, communication tools, potential risk.

In today's digital economy, cyber security has become an important and non-negotiable element of company management. The term may sound simple, but it involves more than just being involved in protecting our integrity or privacy and securing our digital assets and online presence. We all know the role of cyber security with constant innovation and development and its relevance in today's rapid technological advancements.

The integration of digital technologies in the economic transformation can create new risks and threats arising from the emergence of new technologies and features in the digital economy. In order to ensure the security of the national economy during the process of digital economic transformation, it is essential for governments to identify potential risks and threats as implementers and regulators of the economy. The effectiveness of the measures developed and implemented to minimize risks and eliminate threats to national economic security depends on the quality and accuracy of the implemented policy. To analyze the risks and threats posed by cyber threats in the digital economy, a comprehensive approach is necessary and should cover all economic processes, in particular, the relations between the participants involved in the economic process.

A cyber security threat is a malicious activity aimed at destroying, stealing, or disrupting data, critical systems, and digital life in general. Computer viruses, malware attacks, data corruption, and denial of service (DoS) attacks are examples of these risks. As we become more dependent on technology, these cyber security risks have evolved, posing greater risks to people and businesses.

Understanding the dangers of cyber threats is the first step to protecting yourself from them.

Cybersecurity threats to the digital economy come from a variety of places, people, and contexts. Malicious cyber threat actors can include:

Criminal organizations	Organized hacker groups aim to break into organizations for financial gain. These cyber threats use phishing, spam, spyware, and malware for extortion, identity theft, and online scams that operate like corporations, with many employees developing attack vectors and executing attacks.
Nation states	Hostile states can launch cyberattacks against domestic companies and institutions to disrupt communications, cause chaos, and damage.
A terrorist organization	Terrorists carry out cyber attacks aimed at destroying or abusing critical infrastructure, threatening national security, disrupting the economy, and causing civilian harm.
Lying insiders	Employees with legitimate access to company assets abuse their privileges to steal information or damage electronic assets for economic or personal gain. These insider threats can be employees, contractors, suppliers or partners of the target organization

The economic cost of a security breach excludes indirect costs to victims such as opportunity cost, downtime, lost productivity, brand stigma, loss of trust, intellectual property infringement, and damage to employee morale. They also exclude systemic costs such as supply chain impacts on upstream suppliers and downstream customers.

As technology continues to advance, so do the tactics of cybercriminals who seek to exploit vulnerabilities for personal gain.

Cybercrime is the biggest threat to every industry and organization, experts say. the world stores 200 by 2025 zettabytes of data, which is equal to one trillion gigabytes or 10²¹ bytes (1,000,000,000,000,000,000,000). This data is extremely valuable and will continue to be a target for cybercriminals. According to the Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) and McAfee, the economic impact of cybercrime is heaviest in Europe, approaching 0.84 percent of regional GDP. The economic impact of cybercrime in North America is 0.78% of regional GDP. The World Economic Forum reported 1.5 billion attacks through IoT devices in the first half of 2021, an increase of 15% compared to the previous year. IoT device manufacturing is also currently

unregulated, so rapid adoption is compounded by onboard security, common configuration issues, and the frequent use of insecure wireless to connect these devices to networks.

We also look at the profound impact of cyber attacks on individuals, the emotional, financial and psychological consequences that victims may face in the table below.

<i>Financial loss and identity theft</i>	One of the most direct and obvious effects of cyber attacks on individuals is financial loss. Hackers use a variety of methods to steal sensitive financial information, including phishing scams, ransomware, and credit card fraud.
<i>Damage to reputation and relationships</i>	Cyber attacks can also damage an individual's reputation and relationships. Social engineering attacks or leaks of sensitive content can be used to blackmail, embarrass or defame victims, which can seriously damage their personal and professional lives. Rebuilding one's reputation and rebuilding trust with friends, family and colleagues can be difficult after such an event.
<i>Ransomware or denial of service attacks</i>	In cases of ransomware or denial-of-service attacks, individuals can find themselves locked out of critical systems, affecting their productivity and disrupting day-to-day operations. This can lead to missed opportunities, financial losses, and personal and professional failure
<i>Psychological impact and stress</i>	The psychological impact of cyber attacks should not be underestimated. Victims often experience increased stress levels, sleep disturbances, and a constant feeling of weakness. The knowledge that cyber threats are omnipresent can create a constant state of anxiety that affects a person's overall well-being and mental health.
<i>Trust in digital services and technologies</i>	As cyber attacks become more sophisticated, individuals may lose confidence in digital services and technology. This lack of confidence can prevent people from adopting new technologies or engaging in online activities, hindering their ability to take full advantage of the digital world.

These threats can be intentional or unintentional and can lead to data breaches, financial losses, and reputational damage. Understanding the different

types of insider threats and implementing effective mitigation strategies is critical to ensuring strong cybersecurity. Figure 1.

Figure 1. Types of insider threats.

The impact of cyberattacks on individuals extends far beyond the digital realm, affecting their financial stability, emotional well-being, personal relationships, and trust in technology. As we continue to embrace the digital age, it is vital that people are vigilant and proactive in protecting their online presence. Following strong cybersecurity habits, staying up-to-date on the latest threats, and using reputable security tools can greatly reduce your risk of becoming a victim of cyberattacks.

In addition, collaboration between individuals, industries, academia, and governments is critical to combating cybercrime and creating a safer digital environment for all. By working together to address the challenges posed by cyber threats, we can foster a more secure and sustainable digital landscape while protecting everyone's personal well-being and privacy.

References:

1. Kominfo. (2020). Infografis Statistik Transformasi Digital Indonesia 2020. Jakarta: Infografis Statistik Transformasi Digital Indonesia 2020.
2. Kuznetsova, M. A. (2022, Maret 22). ndustry 4.0 Risks and Their Impact on Industrial Organizations - Economy: Problems, Solutions and Prospects.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

3. National Crime Agency. (2020). Cyber crime. Retrieved 20 Maret, 2022, from National Crime Agency: <https://www.nationalcrimeagency.gov.uk/what-we-do/crime-threats/cyber-crime>
4. Piliang, Y. A. (2012). Masyarakat Informasi dan Digital: Teknologi Informasi dan Perubahan Sosial. Jurnal Sositologi, 155.
5. World Economic Forum. (2019). Fourth Industrial Revolution: Beacons of Technology and Innovation in Manufacturing. Cologny: World Economic Forum.
6. Alisher, R., & Fayzi, B. teacher“ s of the department of Information security, Karshi branch of TUIT. SCIENTIFIC REPORTS OF BUKHARA STATE UNIVERSITY, 2.